

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

2025, №6 (20)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

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AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА КЛИНИК
ТИББИЁТ АХБОРОТНОМАСИ
ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

Научный журнал по фундаментальным и клиническим
проблемам медицины
основан в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

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2025, № 6 (20)

Адрес редакции:

Республика Узбекистан, 200100, г.
Бухара, ул. Гиждуванская, 23.

Телефон (99865) 223-00-50

Факс (99866) 223-00-50

Сайт <https://bsmi.uz/journals/fundamental-ya-klinik-tibbiyot-ahborotnomasi/>

e-mail baymuradovravshan@gmail.com

О журнале

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28 мая 2022 года.

Журнал внесен в список
утвержденный приказом № 370/6
от 8 мая 2025 года реестром ВАК
в раздел медицинских наук.

Отпечатано в типографии ООО
“Шарк-Бухоро”. г. Бухара,
ул. Ўзбекистон Муस्ताкиллиги, 70/2.

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WAYS TO IMPROVE THE OUTCOMES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PULMONARY ECHINOCOCCOSIS AND PREVENTION OF RECURRENCE

Ravshanov M.Kh.^{1,3}, Kurbonov N.A.^{2,3}, Davlatov S.S.³, Rakhmanov K.E.⁴

¹Kashkadarya Regional Center of Phthisiology and Pulmonology, Karshi, Uzbekistan

²Kashkadarya Regional Health Department, Karshi, Uzbekistan

³Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sino, Bukhara, Uzbekistan

⁴Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Resume. Relevance. One of the most common causes of parasitic pulmonary invasions encountered in surgical practice is echinococcosis. The Republic of Uzbekistan is also considered an endemic region for this disease. Aim of the study was to improve the effectiveness of treatment in patients with pulmonary echinococcosis through the use of albendazole as a local germicidal agent. **Materials and Methods.** The clinical study included 87 patients diagnosed with pulmonary echinococcosis. **Results.** The comparison group consisted of 45 patients with pulmonary echinococcosis who received albendazole according to the standard treatment regimen. The main group included 42 patients with pulmonary echinococcosis who, in the postoperative period, received oral albendazole at a dose of 5 mg/kg per day in combination with local antiparasitic (contact) treatment of the residual cavity walls using the developed technique. **Conclusion.** The combined use of low-dose systemic albendazole with its topical application as a local germicidal agent according to the proposed method demonstrated a pronounced anti-recurrent effect in the treatment of pulmonary echinococcosis.

Keywords: pulmonary echinococcosis, albendazole, local germicidal agent, recurrence, prevention.

ЎПКА ЭХИНОКОККОЗИНИ ЖАРРОҲЛИК ЙЎЛИ БИЛАН ДАВОЛАШ НАТИЖАЛАРИНИ ЯХШИЛАШ ВА РЕЦИДИВЛАРНИНГ ОЛДИНИ ОЛИШ ЙЎЛЛАРИ

Равшанов М.Х.^{1,3}, Курбонов Н.А.^{2,3}, Давлатов С.С.³, Рахманов К.Э.⁴

¹Қашқадарё вилояти фтизиатрия ва пульмонология маркази, Қарши ш., Ўзбекистон

²Қашқадарё вилояти соғлиқни сақлаш бошқармаси, Қарши ш., Ўзбекистон

³Абу Али ибн Сино номидаги Бухоро давлат тиббиёт институти, Бухоро ш., Ўзбекистон

⁴Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети, Самарқанд ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. Долзарблиги. Жарроҳлик амалиётида аниқланадиган паразитар ўпка инвазияларининг энг кенг тарқалган сабабларидан бири эхинококкоз ҳисобланади. Ўзбекистон ҳам эхинококкоз эндемик бўлган минтақалар қаторига киради. Тадқиқотнинг мақсади - альбендазолни маҳаллий гермицид сифатида қўллаш орқали ўпка эхинококкози билан оғриган беморларни даволаш самарадорлигини оширишидир. **Тадқиқот материаллари ва усуллари.** Клиник тадқиқот ўпка эхинококкози билан касалланган 87 нафар беморни ўз ичига олди. **Тадқиқот натижалари.** Таққослаш гуруҳига альбендазолни стандарт режимга мувофиқ қабул қилган ўпка эхинококкози билан оғриган 45 нафар бемор киритилди. Асосий гуруҳга эса ўпка эхинококкози билан оғриган 42 нафар бемор ажратилди. Ушбу гуруҳ беморларида операциядан кейинги даврда альбендазол кунига 5 мг/кг дозада оғиз орқали қўлланилиши билан бир қаторда, қолдиқ киста бўшлиғи деворларига мазкур препарат билан маҳаллий антипаразитик (контактли) ишлов берилди. **Хулоса.** Альбендазолнинг “кичик” дозаларини ишлаб чиқилган усул бўйича маҳаллий гермицид агент сифатида тизимли қўллаш ўпка эхинококкозида рецидивларга қарши ижобий самара кўрсатишини тасдиқлади.

Калит сўзлар: ўпка эхинококкози, альбендазол, маҳаллий гермицид, рецидив, профилактика.

ПУТИ УЛУЧШЕНИЯ РЕЗУЛЬТАТОВ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ЭХИНОКОККОЗА ЛЕГКИХ И ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ РЕЦИДИВОВ

Равшанов М.Х.^{1,3}, Курбонов Н.А.^{2,3}, Давлатов С.С.³, Рахманов К.Э.⁴

¹Қашқадарьинский областной центр фтизиатрии и пульмонологии, г. Карши, Узбекистан

²Қашқадарьинское областное управление здравоохранения, г. Карши, Узбекистан

³Бухарский государственный медицинский институт имени Абу Али ибн Сино, г. Бухара, Узбекистан

⁴Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, г. Самарканд, Узбекистан

Резюме. Актуальность. Одной из наиболее распространённых причин паразитарных инвазий лёгких, выявляемых в хирургической практике, является эхинококкоз. Республика Узбекистан также

относится к регионам, эндемичным по данному заболеванию. Цель исследования - повышение эффективности лечения больных эхинококкозом лёгких путём применения альбендазола в качестве местного гермицидного средства. Материалы и методы исследования. Клиническое исследование включало 87 пациентов с эхинококкозом лёгких. Результаты исследования. В группу сравнения были включены 45 пациентов с эхинококкозом лёгких, получавших альбендазол по стандартной схеме. Основную группу составили 42 пациента с эхинококкозом лёгких, у которых в послеоперационном периоде альбендазол назначался перорально в дозе 5 мг/кг в сутки в сочетании с местной антипаразитарной (контактной) обработкой стенок остаточной полости данным препаратом по разработанной методике. **Заключение.** Применение «малых» доз альбендазола в сочетании с его местным использованием в качестве топического гермицидного агента по разработанной методике показало наличие выраженного противорецидивного эффекта при эхинококкозе лёгких.

Ключевые слова: эхинококкоз лёгких, альбендазол, местный гермицид, рецидив, профилактика.

Relevance. One of the most common causes of parasitic invasions encountered in surgical practice is echinococcosis [4, 6, 10]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 3 million people worldwide are affected by echinococcosis annually. The Republic of Uzbekistan is also classified as an endemic region for this disease. Due to climatic, geographical, social, and economic factors, various zoonotic foci with different levels of epizootic activity exist in the country. Therefore, the incidence of echinococcosis in humans is directly related to the intensity of epizootic processes in these foci.

Echinococcosis can affect various organs in the human body, with pulmonary echinococcosis being the second most common localization after the liver. Pulmonary echinococcosis is characterized by a severe clinical course, delayed diagnosis, and a high risk of complications. Progressive cyst growth may lead to compression of lung tissue, disruption of bronchial communication, cyst rupture, and secondary infection, all of which pose a serious threat to the patient's life.

Currently, surgery remains the primary treatment modality for pulmonary echinococcosis [4, 6]. However, surgical intervention is associated with significant risk factors, including the patient's general condition, cyst size and localization, presence of complications, and history of previous surgical procedures.

Pulmonary echinococcosis is a severe disease that may be complicated by recurrent cyst formation. Repeated surgical interventions are technically challenging and, in cases of multiple lesions or frequent recurrences, may result in decreased working capacity, disability, or even death. According to various authors, recurrence rates in echinococcosis range from 3% to 54%, depending on the pathogenic characteristics of the parasite, treatment strategy, and preventive measures [1, 3, 10].

To date, there is no unified concept regarding the etiology of recurrence in pulmonary echinococcosis. The literature describes metastatic, implantation, residual, and invasive recurrence theories. Existing diagnostic methods have limited ability to reliably determine the cause of recurrent cyst formation. Consequently, validated diagnostic criteria for identifying recurrence mechanisms have not yet been fully established. Nevertheless, elucidating recurrence causes is crucial for optimizing surgical tactics and improving preventive effectiveness.

Given the above, chemotherapy plays a significant role in preventing echinococcosis recurrence regardless of the underlying mechanisms. Since 1983, the anthelmintic drug albendazole has been widely used for the treatment and prevention of echinococcosis recurrence. In CIS countries, albendazole was recommended as a therapeutic and prophylactic agent at the 2014 Congress of the Association of Hepatobiliary Surgeons of Russia and CIS countries [5].

The most commonly used albendazole regimen involves administration at a dose of 10–20 mg/kg/day, with 3 to 10 treatment courses separated by 14–15-day intervals. This regimen was proposed by Horton (1989) and complies with WHO recommendations.

International studies indicate that albendazole does not exert its effect directly but through its active metabolite, albendazole sulfoxide. Subsequently, it is converted into albendazole sulfone, which has lower biological activity, and is primarily excreted via bile and urine.

The literature extensively reports adverse effects associated with albendazole therapy, often leading to premature discontinuation of treatment. Reported effectiveness of albendazole in preventing echinococcosis recurrence ranges from 40% to 70% [4, 8], which is largely attributed to interindividual variability in drug metabolism influenced by genetic, morphological, and biochemical factors.

Moreover, albendazole standard regimens are applied inconsistently in clinical practice due to the absence of universally accepted optimal criteria, which limits further improvement in treatment outcomes.

In addition to oral administration, albendazole is also used as a local contact germicidal agent, particularly in minimally invasive surgical procedures. Typically, albendazole or hypertonic solutions are instilled into the cyst cavity; however, these approaches may increase the risk of purulent complications.

Aim of the Study. To evaluate the clinical efficacy and safety of combined systemic administration of low-dose albendazole with a locally applied germicidal technique for the prevention of recurrence following surgical treatment of pulmonary echinococcosis.

Materials and Methods. To reduce adverse effects associated with oral or injectable albendazole administration-particularly systemic toxicity and side effects-we developed a combined chemotherapeutic approach involving local contact antiparasitic treatment of pulmonary tissue with albendazole and oral administration of albendazole at a low dose (5 mg/kg/day). The clinical effectiveness of this approach was evaluated.

The study was conducted between 2022 and 2025 in patients treated for pulmonary echinococcosis at the Kashkadarya Regional Phthisiology and Pulmonology Center. The effectiveness of the proposed method in preventing postoperative recurrence of pulmonary echinococcosis was assessed.

The essence of the proposed technique lies in ensuring a targeted local effect by placing a sterile sponge soaked in albendazole solution into the pulmonary echinococcal cyst cavity or onto the surgical wound surface. Tamponade of the pathological focus using a Spongostan-based sponge provided prolonged and directed local germicidal activity.

For this purpose, a sterile sponge measuring 7 × 5 × 1 cm was soaked in 50 ml of 0.9% sodium chloride solution containing albendazole at a concentration of 10% (Figure 1). This approach ensured direct exposure of the drug to the pathological focus while minimizing systemic effects.

Additionally, patients were recommended to receive postoperative oral albendazole at a low dose of 5 mg/kg/day. This comprehensive approach aimed to prevent recurrence of pulmonary echinococcosis through the synergistic effect of local and systemic therapy.

The 10% concentration of albendazole was considered effective and safe, as confirmed by numerous experimental and clinical studies conducted by Erzurumlu et al. [16].

Patient Selection Criteria

The study included patients with pulmonary echinococcosis presenting with:

- multiple echinococcal cysts;
- cysts containing daughter cysts (*Echinococcus hominis*);
- single-chamber cysts (*Echinococcus veterinorum*);
- calcified echinococcal cysts;
- medium and large pulmonary cysts;
- recurrent forms of pulmonary echinococcosis (Table 1).

Table 1.

Distribution of Patients According to Types of Echinococcal Cysts (n = 87)

Cyst type	Total (n=87), %	Comparison group (n=45), %	Main group (n=42), %
Multiple cysts	26 (29.9)	12 (26.7)	14 (33.3)
Cysts with daughter cysts (<i>E. hominis</i>)	56 (64.4)	29 (64.4)	27 (64.3)
Single-chamber cysts (<i>E. veterinorum</i>)	31 (35.6)	17 (37.8)	14 (33.3)
Calcified cysts	7 (8.0)	2 (4.4)	5 (11.9)
Medium and large cysts	24 (27.6)	11 (24.4)	13 (30.9)
Recurrent pulmonary echinococcosis	17 (19.5)	10 (22.2)	7 (16.7)

The comparison group included 45 patients with pulmonary echinococcosis who received albendazole according to the standard regimen (10–12 mg/kg/day, not exceeding 800 mg/day) in three 28-day courses with 14-day intervals.

The main group consisted of 42 patients who, in the postoperative period, received oral albendazole at a dose of 5 mg/kg/day in combination with local contact antiparasitic treatment of the residual cyst cavity walls using albendazole.

Results. After discharge, all patients were placed under scheduled medical follow-up. Follow-up included chest radiography and computed tomography, as well as regular clinical monitoring. Additionally, biochemical blood parameters were assessed every 6 months for 1.5–2 years.

Analysis of the results revealed recurrence of pulmonary echinococcosis in 5 patients (11.1%) in the comparison group, predominantly within the first year of follow-up. No recurrence cases were observed in the main group during the entire observation period.

Furthermore, no local (purulent complications, infection of the residual cavity) or systemic (hepatotoxicity, allergic reactions) adverse effects were observed in patients treated using the proposed method. The dynamics of biochemical parameters confirmed preservation of overall physiological stability and the safety of the treatment approach.

The obtained data demonstrate the high clinical efficacy of the developed combined approach in preventing recurrence of pulmonary echinococcosis.

Conclusion. Despite the relatively limited sample size, the results of this study demonstrate that the combination of systemic administration of low-dose albendazole with locally applied germicidal treatment using the developed methodology is effective in preventing recurrence of pulmonary echinococcosis. The proposed approach not only reduces the risk of disease recurrence but also minimizes the likelihood of local and systemic complications and is well tolerated by patients. These findings indicate that this method represents a promising and practical strategy for postoperative prophylaxis in pulmonary echinococcosis.

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For citation: Ravshanov M.Kh., Kurbonov N.A., Davlatov S.S., Rakhmanov K.E. Ways to improve the outcomes of surgical treatment of pulmonary echinococcosis and prevention of recurrence // *Bulletin of Fundamental and Clinic Medicine*. – 2025. – № 6(20). – P. 1648–1651. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18150026>